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Design and Synthesis of Flavonoid Derivatives as Anti-inflammatory Drug

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ABSTRACT

A series of 2-(3'-aminesubstituted)-7-hydroxyl-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one amine derivatives has been synthesized on the basis of molecular docking results. The novel derivatives prepared by condensation of 2,4-Dihydroxyacetophenone (1.40 ml) and 3-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.01 mole) through Claisen-Schmidt condensation reaction. Novel flavone derivatives were access for anti-inflammatory activity by using carrageenan induced rat paw edema method. Among the synthesized compounds (t, v, w, k) shows good anti-inflammatory activity comparable to reference drug (Celecoxib).

Keywords: Molecular docking; Synthetic flavone; Claisen Schmidt condensation reaction; Anti-inflammatory; Celecoxib

INTRODUCTION

Flavonoids based on the backbone of 2-phenyl-4H-chromen-4-one (2-phenyl-1-benzopyran-4-one). The molecular formula of flavone molecule is $C_{15}H_{10}O_2$. It has three-ring skeletons, $C_6-C_3-C_6$ and the rings are referred to as A, C and B rings, respectively. They are found in seeds, citrus fruits, olive oil, tea and red wine, vegetables, nuts, stems and flowers, honey and are commonly consumed with the human diet. 2-(3'-aminesubstituted)-7-hydroxyl-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one derivatives these are Non-Steroidal Anti Inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) exhibit their effect by inhibiting COX enzymes and by blocking the synthesis of prostaglandins [1-3].

In a literature, revealed that, flavone shows good to moderate anti-inflammatory activity. It is also observed that the flavone moiety should possess following characteristic pharmacophore pattern which is essential for binding to cyclooxygenase enzyme and their by its inhibition. Flavone possess following pharmacophoric pattern (Figure 1).

- The ligand should possess suitably positioned hetero atom, which strongly interact with heme iron.
- The ligand should have a hydrophobic spacer moiety between heme coordinating group and hydrogen bond acceptor moiety.
- Cyclooxygenase inhibitors need a chemical group that is able to accept H-bond from serine 478 present in active site.

Figure 1: Pharmacophore pattern of cyclooxygenase inhibitors.

Figure 6: Synthesis of novel flavone derivatives.

Table 3: Derivatives of novel flavonoids.

Sr. no.	Compound	-R/Ar	S. No.	Compound	-R/Ar
1	A	Methylamino	5	l	Ethylmethylamino
2	B	Ethylamino	6	t	<i>p</i> -Methylaniline,
3	C	Propylamino	7	v	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline
4	K	Diethylamino	8	w	<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline

Table 4: Characterization data for 2-(3'-aminesubstituted)-7- hydroxyl-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one derivatives.

Sr. No.	Code	Molecular formula	Mol. weight (g/mol)	Yield %	Melting point (°C)	Rf-value	U.V. λ_{max} (nm)
1	a	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ NO ₃	267	63.12	178-180	0.6	241.6
2	b	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ NO ₃	280	57	184-185	0.82	309.2
3	c	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₃	295	57.86	187-190	0.84	297
4	k	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ NO ₃	309	66.21	179-182	0.62	298
5	l	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₃	295	59.09	181-183	0.47	319
6	t	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ NO ₃	365	72.25	190-195	0.72	340

7	v	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ NO ₃ Cl	375	69.24	192-196	0.82	290
8	w	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₅	344	70.16	190-194	0.68	318

Table 5: Anti-inflammatory activity obtained by carrageenan induced rat paw edema method and comparative study of inhibition (%I) for anti-inflammatory activity by carrageenan induced rat paw edema method.

Sr. No.	Groups	Mean of paw volume (mL)				± SEM				% Inhibition of paw edema			
		0 h	1 h	2 h	3 h	0 h	1 h	2 h	3 h	0 h	1 h	2 h	3 h
1	Control	0.51	0.57	0.56	0.55	0.087	0.098	0.095	0.098	--	--	--	--
2	A	0.56	0.47	0.46	0.45	0.098	0.142	0.096	0.122	--	17.55	17.86	18.19
3	B	0.56	0.47	0.46	0.45	0.098	0.142	0.096	0.122	--	16.2	16.8	17.02
4	C	0.57	0.48	0.46	0.46	0.098	0.102	0.096	0.096	--	16.79	16.04	17.37
5	K	0.57	0.43	0.38	0.32	0.08	0.128	0.124	0.107	--	23.7	33.14	44.03
6	L	0.51	0.43	0.46	0.4	0.102	0.143	0.149	0.145	--	24.57	25	27.28
7	T	0.57	0.43	0.38	0.3	0.098	0.128	0.128	0.109	--	30.7	39.14	40.03
8	V	0.57	0.43	0.42	0.41	0.098	0.143	0.149	0.16	--	21.46	24	24.46
9	W	0.51	0.36	0.3	0.2	0.102	0.092	0.088	0.052	--	43.26	43.75	45.08
10	Celecoxib	0.54	0.38	0.38	0.27	0.096	0.104	0.104	0.087	--	33..34	32.15	45.91

CONCLUSION

From present work it is prove that novel series of 2-(3'-aminesubstituted)-7- hydroxyl-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one derivatives has been synthesized, physical characteristics followed by the anti-inflammatory screening occurs. Derivatives (t, v, w, k) shows the good anti-inflammatory activity when compared against vehicle treated control and standard celecoxib.

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